

THEORETICAL INVESTIGATION OF TRANSITIVE AND INTRANSITIVE VERBS IN ENGLISH GRAMMAR

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Abstract: The article deals with theories about investigation of transitive and intransitive verbs in English grammar. On the other hand, article covered examples and full explanation of the theme.

Keywords: valency, obligatory noun, ambitransitive, ditransitive verbs, major participant, commonly bitransitive, polypersonal agree, functional grammar.

In linguistics, transitivity is a property of verbs that relates to whether a verb can take direct objects and how many such objects a verb can take. It is closely related to valency, which considers other verb arguments in addition to direct objects. The obligatory noun phrases and prepositional phrases determine how many arguments a predicate has. Obligatory elements are considered arguments while optional ones are never counted in the list of arguments. Traditional grammar makes a binary distinction between intransitive verbs that cannot take a direct object (such as fall or sit in English) and transitive verbs that take one direct object (such as throw, injure, kiss in English). In practice, many languages (including English) interpret the category more flexibly, allowing: ditransitive verbs, verbs that have two objects; or even ambitransitive verbs, verbs that can be used as both a transitive verb and an intransitive verb[1]. Further, some verbs may be idiomatically transitive, while, technically, intransitive. This may be observed in the verb walk in the idiomatic expression “To walk the dog”.

In functional grammar, transitivity is considered to be a continuum rather than a binary category as in traditional grammar. The "continuum" view takes a more semantic approach. One way it does this is by taking into account the degree to which an action affects its object (so that the verb see is described as having "lower transitivity" than the verb kill). Formal transitivity is associated with a variety of semantic functions across languages. Crosslinguistically, Hopper and Thompson (1980) have proposed to decompose the notion of transitivity into ten formal and semantic features (some binary, some scalar); the features argued to be associated with the degree of transitivity. Nass has argued at length for the following two points:

1. Though formally a broad category of phenomena, transitivity boils down to a way to maximally distinguish the two participants involved. Major participants are describable in terms of the semantic features which makes them distinctive from each other[2]. Different combinations of these binary values will yield different types of participants, which are then compatible or incompatible with different verbs. Individual languages may, of course, make more fine-grained distinctions. The notion of transitivity, as well as other notions that today are the basics of linguistics, was first introduced by the Stoics and the Peripatetic school, but they probably referred to the whole sentence containing transitive or intransitive verbs, not just to the verb. The discovery of the Stoics was later used and developed by the philologists of the Alexandrian school and later grammarians.

A transitive verb is a verb that accepts one or more objects. Transitivity is traditionally thought a global property of a clause, by which activity is transferred from an agent to a patient. Transitive verbs can be classified by the number of objects they require. Verbs that accept only two arguments, a subject and a single direct object, are monotransitive. Verbs that accept two objects, a direct object and an indirect object, are ditransitive, or less commonly bitransitive. An example

of a ditransitive verb in English is the verb to give, which may feature a subject, an indirect object, and a direct object: John gave Mary the book. Verbs that take three objects are tritransitive. In English a tritransitive verb features an indirect object, a direct object, and a prepositional phrase – as in I'll trade you this bicycle for your binoculars – or else a clause that behaves like an argument – as in I bet you a pound that he has forgotten. Not all descriptive grammars recognize tritransitive verbs[3]. The concept of valency is related to transitivity. The valency of a verb considers all the arguments the verb takes, including both the subject and all of the objects. In contrast to valency, the transitivity of a verb only considers the objects. Subcategorization is roughly synonymous with valency, though they come from different theoretical traditions.

Many languages, such as Hungarian, mark transitivity through morphology; transitive verbs and intransitive verbs behave in distinctive ways[4]. In languages with polypersonal agreement, an intransitive verb will agree with its subject only, while a transitive verb will agree with both subject and direct object. In other languages the distinction is based on syntax. It is possible to identify an intransitive verb in English, for example, by attempting to supply it with an appropriate direct object:

He kissed her hand—transitive verb.

She injured him—transitive verb.

What did you throw?—transitive verb.

Verbs can be so tricky that even the best grammar students might be often confounded by the difference between transitive and intransitive verbs. The confusion with the use of the transitive and intransitive verbs can be resolved as a grammar point becomes clear with an understanding of objects. When using a dictionary to look up verbs, we may have been puzzled by the abbreviations vi (intransitive verb) and vt (transitive verb). Kline and Demuth, Berry, Azar and Hagen, Crystal, and Francez claim that it is the object of any given sentences that

makes the difference, a clear grammatical point that may serve as a clue to determine if the sentences have a transitive verb or intransitive verb. So, what is the confusion all about? Why should the students know the difference between transitive and intransitive verbs? Why is it important to know the difference between transitive and intransitive verbs? Understanding the different functions of those two verbs can help any students dealing with the use of those two types of verbs avoid grammatical mistakes, such as incomplete sentences that may result into misleading sentences that lose its exact meaning. Students, particularly the speakers of other languages, often have difficulty determining which verbs require an object, and which do not[5]. When students confuse transitive and intransitive verbs, the sentences they construct both orally and in written may be incomplete. As mentioned above, an action verb which has an object, either direct or indirect, is called a transitive verb, while an action verb which does not have an object is called an intransitive verb.

To sum up it should be noted that b-y making deep research and studying the topic “Transitive and intransitive verbs” we had an opportunity to learn and understand that teaching and learning process related to verbs in English as a foreign language has been considered a challenge for students. During the working on this topic, we have realized that the category of verbs has been didactically described and formulated in various ways, which makes the topic become more complex. Working with the literary work given for the analysis of transitive and intransitive verbs was confusing since the theories given by grammarians are used in the different way by the authors which means the theory and practice are not always similarly approached.

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